

THE IMPORTANCE OF ACCOUNTING FOR LARGE SHEAR DEFORMATIONS ON MODELLING MATRIX FAILURE OF THERMOPLASTIC AND THERMOSET COMPOSITES

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The use of thermoplastic composite materials is gaining momentum in the transportation sector due to their improved mechanical properties, ‘unlimited’ shelf life and it offers a number of advantages that can benefit cost-efficient and high-volume manufacturing such as out-of-autoclave consolidation and thermoplastic welding [1]. However, their mechanical behaviour and the validity of analysis methodologies that were originally developed for thermoset composites are not yet well understood. A numerical investigation is performed to study different approaches [2,3] that represent matrix cracks in continuum damage models and results are compared to benchmarks from literature. Furthermore, virtual coupon tests are performed and compared against experimental data from both thermoplastic (AS4D/PEKK) and thermoset (AS4/8552) composites [2]. It was found that traditional strain based continuum damage models have difficulty in accurately predicting matrix failure and their interaction with delaminations due to the presence of large shear deformations. The failure modes are highly influenced at both the local and global scale (Figure 1) and it is shown that accounting for large shear deformations in continuum damage models is important for both thermoset and thermoplastic composites.

Figure 1. Matrix failure due to large deformation at the local (left) and global (right) scale

References

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